

**CYPRUS INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE STUDIES AND RESEARCH
ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE DEPARTMENT**

**THE IMPACT OF LIQUIDITY RISK MANAGEMENT
ON COMMERCIAL BANK'S FINANCIAL
PERFORMANCE.
A CASE STUDY OF SIERRA LEONE AND KENYA
COMMERCIAL BANKS**

(MSc THESIS)

JOSEPH KANU

NICOSIA – 2021

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JOSEPH KANU

**SUPERVISOR
ASST. PROF. DR. ASIL AZIMLI**

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INSTITUTE OF GRADUATE STUDIES AND RESEARCH**

ACCOUNTING AND FINANCE DEPARTMENT

THESIS APPROVAL CERTIFICATE

The thesis study of Accounting and Finance Department graduate student Joseph Kanu with student number 21901746 **entitled the impact of liquidity risk management on commercial bank's financial performance (a case study of sierra leone and Kenya commercial banks)** has been approved with unanimity/majority of votes by the jury and has been accepted as a Master of Accounting and Finance Thesis.

Thesis Defense Date: 08/02/2021

Jury Members

Signature

1) Thesis Supervisor

Asst. Prof. Dr. Asil Azimli,

.....

2) Member

Asst. Prof. Dr. Ahmad Abu Alrub

.....

3) Member

Asst. Prof. Dr. Hasan Rustemoglu

.....

**Director of the Institute
Prof. Dr. Tahir CELIK**

DECLARATION

Name and Surname: Joseph Kanu

Title of The Thesis: The impact of liquidity risk management on commercial bank's financial performance (a case study of Sierra Leone and Kenya commercial banks).

Supervisor(s): Asst. Prof. Dr. Asil Azimli.

Year: 2021

I hereby declare that all information in this document has been obtained and presented in accordance with academic rules and ethical conduct. I also declare that, as required by these rules and conduct, I have fully cited and referenced all material and results that are not original to this work.

I hereby declare that the Cyprus International University, Institute of Graduate Studies and Research is allowed to store and make available electronically the present thesis.

Date: //2021

Signature: _____

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ABSTRACT

This study was therefore carried out to evaluate the impact of liquidity risk management on commercial bank's financial performance, taking into consideration Sierra Leone and Kenya. The research concentrates on 25 out of 35 commercial banks based in Sierra Leone and Kenya during the year 2009-2018. Secondary data have been collected for 10 years between 2009 and 2018. A Descriptive statistical analysis and panelized multiple regression models using the generalized moments methods (GMM) that assesses the relationship regarding liquidity risk management and commercial banks' financial performance. The analysis of the regression shows a significantly negative relationship between liquidity risk management of commercial banks' financial performance in Sierra Leone and Kenya. The studies found that liquidity risk management accounted for 26.7% of the difference in return on the asset over the study period. The Liquid assets-to-total assets, loan-to-deposit ratio, and total liabilities to total assets account for a substantial increase, led by total revenues. Further findings from this study had been that the liquid assets-to- total assets has a negative effect on the commercial bank's financial performance. It also indicates how banks must therefore be ensuring that they retain an optimum amount of liquid assets that usually provide lower returns while at the same time being able to satisfy customer requirements. This recommends that as the study developed an adverse relationship in the management of liquidity risks and financial returns of Sierra Leone and Kenyan commercial banks, this makes it more important to management not only to improve the practice of effective liquidity management by maximizing return on asset (ROA) but also to put banks on a sound foundation to withstand risks that might arise in financial matters.

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Keywords: Liquidity Risk Management, Financial Performance, Sierra Leone Commercial Banks, Kenya Commercial Banks.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BSL	Bank of Sierra Leone
ROA	Return on Asset
NIM	Net Interest Margin
LATA	Liquid asset to total asset
LDR	Loan to deposit ratio
LRMR	Liquidity risk management ratio
CAR	Capital adequacy ratio
CBK	Central Bank of Kenya
IMF	International Monetary Fund
MFBS	Micro Finance Banks
MFC	Mortgage Finance Company
NSC	Nairobi Securities Exchange

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Study Background

The continued life of banks is driven by liquidity. Their maturing transition role in the economy gives rise to questions regarding bank liquidity. In general, banks accept deposits of short-term demand, loaned to enterprises. The banks loan a substantial part of their deposits in the marginal banking network and maintain a small portion of their deposits. Banks are exposed to liquidity risk to provide this important social function for the economy. Through keeping large cash reserves of liquid asset that are able to increase to pay mature securities during every financial crisis, banks may mitigate this risk. (Davies, 2014)

According to Basel III, Liquidity has become a bank's ability to finance increase in asset and fulfil commitments as necessary without inadmissible losses as required. The essential function of banks in converting deposits of short-term loans into long-term loans enables banks, both of a systemic nature and a market as a whole, more prone to liquidity risks. Almost all other financial operation or engagement has consequences for the liquidity of a bank. Efficient liquidity risk management aims to guarantee the capacity of a bank to fulfill the volatile cash flow requirements that are influenced by various factors and other agent's action. Liquidity risk management is highly critical as a liquidity shortage can have system-wide implications for a single entity.

Given that financial assets like cash and government bonds typically had a lower return, keeping them would trigger a bank's opportunity cost. Without legislation, it's also fair to assume the banks to keep liquid assets to optimize the financial output of the bank. Also, policymakers can enable relatively large holdings of liquid assets, for example, if the consistency of the overall financial system is seen as benefiting. This study focuses upon the evaluation impact of liquidity risk management on Commercial Banks ' financial performance of Sierra Leone and Kenya.

For several firms, the banking sector is seen as a significant source of funding. To evaluate and weigh the adequacy and efficiency of the banking sector, it is important to take into account the risk information and how uncertainties are handled. The

liquidity risk of the bank among all financial risks is necessary to consider. The unfortunate financial status of the banks would reduce the bank's valuation. Liquidity risk control must be efficiently and carefully controlled and handled. (Iqbal, 2012).

Banks often seek to optimize profitability while at the same time seeking to ensure adequate liquidity to depend on their ability to finance deposits in the depositors' minds by ensuring regular payments of interest or return on deadlines and performing all other liability obligations as agreed. In order to achieve these objectives, banks must systematically track, retain, and manage the asset and liability portfolios, with the various risks involved in such fields in mind. (Charumathi, 2008).

The banks' vital role in converting the duration short-term loan deposits into long-term credit emerges from the liquidity risk. Also, the bank cannot fund rises in assets without unacceptable losses and to satisfy obligations when they occur. A bank is at risk of not being able to comply with its obligations due to failure to liquidate assets or insufficient sources of finance. (Decker, 2012).

1.1.1 Liquidity Risk Management

The management of liquidity risk is a risk that banks either fail to deliver on their obligations in respect of depositors or fund assets when they emerge without overpricing or losses. This risk arises if the depositors plan to jointly withdraw more capital than the bank has at hand, or if the borrower does not fulfill its financial obligations to the banks. In other words, there are two cases of liquidity risk. First of all, in their relationship with the banks, it happens symmetrically to borrowers, for instance, when they wish to end the loans, but borrowers cannot afford that. Furthermore, when banks wish to refund their deposits, but the banks cannot afford it, they occur concerning partnerships between banks and their depositors. In practical terms, banks frequently find disparities (gaps) between the liability side and that of the asset, which must be covered by recognizing liquid liabilities but investing in illiquidity. If such a gap is not resolved by a bank, liquidity risks may emerge, followed by unnecessary impacts including the insolvency, credibility risk and the government bailout risk, and. The bank's lack of liquidity management or inefficiencies is attributable to the magnitude of the pressure of liquidity, the planning of liquid

instruments of the bank, its liquidity pressure situation, and the bank's inability to find domestic or foreign sources of liquidity. (Kumar &Yadav, 2013).

The financial services sector's integrated risk management system for all financial institutions (Majid, 2003). An optimal way of defining, measuring, managing, and minimizing the liquidity risk should be a well-managed bank. The MFB is helped to rapidly define the factors of liquidity risk with in event of losses by a well-defined framework. The Statement of financial position of the banks is increasingly complex and reliant on capital markets which have made managing liquidity risks more difficult (Guglielmo, 2008). Furthermore, he suggests that banks with expanded capital markets participation must be fully aware of the risks involved.

Liquidity management is a crucial banking feature and an important part of the liquidity risk management process. Many banking operations rely on a bank's capacity to offer liquidity to its customers. The liquidity of a bank affects most banking transactions and/or obligations. Banks at the institutional and systemic/market level are especially vulnerable to liquidity problems. Deposit sources (that provide more funding) increase the uncertainty of funds, considering that certain creditors are much more vulnerable to market and credit occurrences than the others. Diversifying the sources and maturities of funding helps a bank to escape the risk of one source of funding intensity. Bank liquidity policies should include the framework of the Risk Management (Decision-making), liquidity management and funding policy, a set of regulatory standards, and a set of option liquidity preparation procedures, especially in times of crisis. (Alzorqan, 2015).

A bank is in control of effective liquidity risk management. To withstand a variety of stress events, such as failure or damage to both unsafe and stable funding sources, and also banks should develop a vigorous/robust liquidity risk management framework that provides adequate liquidity, such as a buffer of unburdened, unique liquid assets. The supervisors must determine the adequacy and liquidity status of both a liquidity risk management system of a bank and should take immediate action if a banking system is inadequate in either field to safeguard depositors and minimize possible harm to the financial sector. (Kumar &Yadav, 2013).

Liquidity risk management strategies are continually changing in able to serve the needs of rising contradictions in various financing sources. Fund's problems will negatively impact administrators who are unable to implement plans that fix present conditions. The liquidity risk management measures include setting strategic guidelines, incorporating liquidity risk management into the management of assets, retaining liquidity risk measurement schemes, tracking and monitoring current capacity and expected liquidity position. The bank's financial status and also its prevailing trends in the changing financial sector would also be periodically evaluated. (Decker, 2000)

Internationally, over several years, a large agreement has developed upon its significance of controlling and the need to manage the liquidity risk to maintain the sustainability of individual banks and the stability of the overall banking system. Even so, there have been several variations as to the transposition into principles and guidelines of this theory. While changes in the international bank structure have expanded banks' technological solutions to liquidity risk management over recent times, these reforms have often minimized the means of such risk. The financial recession has underlined a need for effective liquidity management in the banking sectors, requiring the management and control of liquidity in usual and stress-related situations by both regulatory bodies and corporate management, combining improved treasury with several other liquidity functions and growing the value of liquidity risk as part of risk management. The recession has stressed the deficiency of internal self-regulation and the requirement of national and foreign legislation to take account of the need for general rules restricting banks' appetite for liquidity risk while pursuing banking stability and reducing competitive disparities. The risk of liquidity is hard to measure and too many forces render it unsuitable for the prevention of a need for money. Proper management strategy allows the liquidity risk to be analyzed concerning the effect region, the time scale, the cause, and where it arises. Following the analyzes of these 4 factors, model risk metrics must be defined, indicators established to monitored, operating limits set, and related organizational problems defined. This study discusses, after an analysis of key economic aspects of liquidity risk, new International rules to create a common risk liquidity management system in

the banks, though gradually, and gives the main economic and managing implications for banking management that these Regulations would bring about. (Ruozi & Ferrari, 2013).

1.1.2 Commercial Banks Financial Performance

The performance is the ability to function efficiently and profitably, to expand, to increase and to react to various risks and prospects. (Mawanda, 2008). As well as for financial performance assessment purposes, the variables (ROA), (ROE), and (NIM) being used. ROA is only discussed in this article. Apart from profitability, some of the indicators of commercial success in the banking system are liquidity, allocation of credit and trying to grab customers. Suitable performance indicators help organizations to lead their action to achieve their policy priorities in accordance with the available literature.

The return on asset, return on equity and return on sales variables, are indicators used as accounting based performance measures. All is measured by the division of net profits by total assets, total share capital and overall net sales respectively. Return on capital equity (ROE) is also a portion of the shareholders' net sales returns. The ROE is a profitability ratio that calculates a company's ability to produce income from the investments of its shareholders in the bank. ROE is also a measure of how efficient equity funding is being used by management to fund activities and enlarge the banking sector. Higher ratios are often successful than lower ratios which demonstrate how efficient the bank is at producing income, but the ratios of other firms in the sector have to be compared. Many investors mostly want to measure the return on equity funds at the start of the cycle and the end of a time frame seeing the variation in return. It also helps to track an organization's success and ability to maintain a positive income pattern. You will get a better understanding of historical development by averaging ROE over the past 5 to 10 years. (Ng'ang'a, 2017).

The financial performance of commercial banks examines how performance is rewarded by higher profits by increased market shares (Thomas & Ramaswamy, 1996). In (Drago, 1990), financial results contribute to revenue growth, higher investment return (ROI), and higher sales return (ROS), higher equity returns (ROE), and higher earnings per share. However, profitability and growth can be described as

the common ratios that evaluate organizational performance; ROA, ROI, ROE and ROS, sales growth, market shares, stock price and growth in sales, liquidity and operating performance. (Thomas & Ramaswamy, 1996).

1.1.3 The relationship between liquidity risk management and commercial banks financial performance

(Kibuchi, 2015), findings showed that the value of the cash balance was improved during the studied five-year period, while liquidity deficits in commercial banks in Kenya were increased during the years studied. The return-on-assets (ROA), the cash balance and the amount of company also have a favorable relation, but the positive relationship between the return-on-assets (ROA) and the liquidity gap has been slightly small. This study also concluded that the risk of liquidity not only influences a bank's performance, but also its credibility, and this could lead to a lack of trust among depositors if they are not supported with funds promptly. Also, a bad liquidity position will result in regulatory penalties and it is therefore essential that banks retain a stable liquidity position at all times. The study suggested that banks retain sufficient levels of liquidity for short-run capital assets in order to achieve income for banks.

(Maaka, 2013). The analysis undertaken in Kenya has indicated that economic features are greatly impacted by a liquidity gap amidst the management of liquidity risk and commercial banks financial results.

(Li, 2007) did find that the profitability liquidity results are varied and therefore not important, indicating that liquidity impact conclusions remain doubtful and further investigation necessary.

(Lartey et al, 2013) study focusing on listed banks in Ghana reported a poor positive relationship with liquidity and financial returns in the study.

The (Lamberg & Valming, 2009) findings recommend that liquidity adjustment techniques have no major impact on ROA. The only positive impact on ROA was improved liquidity projections and short-term funding during the global recession. Furthermore, the value of the critical liquidity ratios between the study time-points was found to have no effects.

(Akinwumi & Michael, 2007) suggested that a significant association exists between liquidity and ROA, and further recommended that banks review their liquidity management strategy for increasing the optimization of shareholder returns in their investigation of the management of liquidity and banks' profitable returns in Nigeria.

(Nyabateh, 2013) has concluded that liquidity management in Kenya is not the only factor affecting financial features that are profit generating banks; there are several other variables that can affect ROA and thus further affirm that liquidity and financial returns are weakly linked to banks.

1.1.4 The Commercial Banking Institutions

This scope of this study deals with commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya from the year 2009 – 2018. Sierra Leone's financial sector comprises of the Central Bank, 14 commercial banks, (3 local), 14 micro-financing licensed associations, 17 Cooperative banks, 51 associations of financial services and 50 registered foreign exchange offices/Bureau.

In order to provide a stable and resilient financial system in the economy, the Sierra Leone Central Bank is continuing to control and supervise financial services providers. While the financial sector remains superficial, frenetic attempts to expand access to financial services and improve the financial markets have been stepped up. It included incorporating technology to increase cross-bank transfers, developing a security registry, improving the credit reference bureau and supporting mobile money services (BSL Annual Report, 2017).

The Kenya Central Bank as the governing authorities, 44 banks (43 commercial banks, 1(one) mortgage financing corporation – (MFC), 7 representing branches of international banks, 9 Microfinance Banks (MFBs), 2 Credit References Bureau Offices (CRBs), and 101 forex bureaus were composed by the banking sector on 31 December 2013. Of the 44 banking institutions, 30 are local banks, 3 have public ownership and 27 are private owners while 14 have international ownership. The international financial institutions include 10 global local banks and 4 foreign corporate banking offices.

In the period ended December 2013, the banking sector showed improved results. During the year, pre-tax income rose by 16.6% in the sector. The Total net assets and total bank deposits documented a growth rate of 16.0% and 13.3%, respectively. According to the result of profit retention and extra capital injection, the sector also reported significantly higher levels capitalization. As in December 2012, the rating of the banking sector remained high.

The creation of Sierra Leone's financial sector was generally in line with the 2009 FSDP which, among other acts, is predicated in the enhancement of financial stability by expanding and strengthening the financial sector. Prudential requirements were reached by banks at the end of 2014. Especially in comparison to 2013, however, the number of banks not achieving capital adequacy, minimum liquidity and non-performing loan ratios expanded. (UNDP 2016 Report).

From 2013 to June 2016, the bank sector's liquidity levels were considerably higher than the regulatory minimum liquidity ratio, which shows that banks have large quantities of liquid assets to cover their business requirements. Over that duration, non-performing loans rose dramatically in the gross credit ratio. The return on assets in late 2011 was 3.8% and decreased considerably to 1.85% at the end of 2016 (IMF Report, 2016).

To assess the quality of the financial sector, the Reserve Bank of Kenya has introduced a scheme of capital adequacy and asset efficiency, the quality of management, profits, and liquidity (CAMEL). The banking sector was highly valued in 2013, which was comparable in 2012. In December 2013, the institutions graded 18, 20, and 5 respectively as good, satisfactory, and fair. The minimum liquidity ratio of 20 percent is expected from CBK. The amount of liquidity demonstrates the capacity of the bank to finance asset rises and to meet bonds when they become due. The amount of liquidity demonstrates the capacity of banks to finance asset rises and fulfill their debt. Liquidity, as liquidity in banks shortfalls can potentially cause a crisis in the banking sector because of its unified activity, is among the significant indicators of financial stability. The average liquidity of the banking sector was above the statutory basic threshold of 12% in the period from 12 months to December 2013 with the minimum

requirement being met by all banks. In December 2013, the liquidity rate was 38.6%, related to 41.9% in 2012. (Sierra Leone report on supervisions of banks, 2013-18).

1.2 The Research Problem

The theory for liabilities management also claimed that there is no justification for banks to offer customers self-liquidation credit and maintain liquid assets for the purposes of meeting their anticipated liquidity needs (Emmanuel, 1997).

Different hypotheses and empirical findings have tried to define the main relationship between liquidity risk management of banks financial performance to boost sound and robust financial systems. The theory of shifting capacity asserts that banks are not only important for growing liquidity but are also in a stronger position to fulfill their economic obligations to preserve their ability to hold assets that can be transferred easily without delay and without substantial losses (Bwacha & Xi, 2018).

Liquidity concerns can have an adverse impact on a bank's financial performance and solvency. Most studies have found that the link between banks performance and liquidity is important, whereas others show a poor, strong relationship. In 2013, commercial banks in Kenya recorded strong results surpassing the country's overall economic growth. In 2013, the Kenyan banking sector was ranked strongly by means of the CAMEL, asset quality, capital adequacy, quality of management, benefit, and liquidity (Kenya Banking Supervision Report, 2013).

In the distribution of economic capital of countries, commercial banks play a critical role. They are constantly channeling depositor funds to investors. You can do that because you produce the income required to meet your operating costs. In other words, banks must be profitable for efficient intermediation. In addition to the intermediary role, banks' financial output has important consequences for countries' economic development. The shareholders are compensated for their contributions by good financial results. In exchange, this stimulates more investment and leads to economic development. In comparison, poor bank performance can cause financial collapse and crisis that can negatively affect economic growth, (Ongore, & Kusa, 2013).

(Li, 2007) liquidity of the firm results on profitability are mixed and not material, that liquidity effect findings remain doubtful and additional research is essential.

The control of liquidity risks is synonymous with uncertainty as all other factors that can affect the financial achievement of banking institutions. (Kumar, 2012) asserts in a highly competitive market environment that liquidity risk management and profitability is a crucial problem. He also claimed that income and liquidity are inverses. Increasing net assets would reduce profitability.

(Boedeleau & Graham, 2010) warned that the retention additional liquid assets could decrease the financial capacity of the banks beyond that stage.

Researchers have undertaken a great deal to develop the liquidity risk management and banks' financial performance relationship at diverse locations. Although the scope, methodology, time, and background of their analysis vary, their corresponding outcomes indicate that the affiliation between the management of liquidity and financial performance has always been complicated. Therefore, this thesis therefore aims to discuss the question; How are liquidity risk management and Sierra Leone and Kenya's bank sector financial returns related?

1.3 Aim of the Study

The study defines the evaluation of the Impact of management liquidity risk on financial performance on commercial bank. The research also aims to examine the relationship between liquidity risk management and financial performance of commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya.

1.4 The Significance of the Study

In the current recession, the significance of efficient banking liquidity management has been emphasized. In addition, policymakers are developing new Liquidity requirements that will improve the constancy and robustness of the financial system. Liquidity concerns will adversely impact a bank's financial results and solvency. Thus, it is necessary that industry practitioners acknowledge the influence related to the management of liquidity on commercial banks' financial performance. Top management in Bank's executive committee will be using the report to enhance their efficiency. The outcomes of this study will be extremely relevant from a policy point of view. When policy makers formulate standards settings determining the appropriate

level of bank liquidity, which help to guarantee sufficient stability in the international economic market, the trade between liquidity shock tolerance as well as the expense of retaining lower liquid assets should be taken into account. Although retaining the liquid assets would increase the resilience of banks against financial instability and thus minimize the negative external costs they could place on other financial intermediaries, holding too many can bring substantial costs as regards lower profits. The study improves the academic awareness and helps other academics who might like to assess the financial efficiency of liquidity risk management of the banking institution.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This review emphasizes on the theoretical and empirical studies of the research showing the connection between the liquidity risk management and financial performance of financial institutions in Sierra Leone and Kenya. The first section, has the same underlying theoretical context is discussed and, in the second section, also addresses the determinates of banks' performance and, in essence, a review of the studies carried out.

2.2 The Literature Theoretical Review

The emphasis of this chapter is on liquidity risk management theories. This subdivision will explore four hypotheses that are considered to be relevant to the research subject. It also covers the performance determinants of commercial banks and the study of empirical studies on the subject.

2.2.1 The Theory of Loanable Funds

This theory suggests how the commercial bank's liquidity is acquired automatically by the personality of a short-term lending and by the financing of working capital, where the borrowers effectively repay their loan proceeds after completing their trade flows. Theory suggests that because of the duration of these investment's anticipated return period, Banks really shouldn't loan money to that purchase for property or retail products or even for investment in securities, whether this concept is sufficient for traders to finance their particular trading activities and for short durations. (Alshatti, 2015),

The loanable funds theory is centered on this same idea that the interest rate, that is to say the price per unit of time used for the use of such funds, must be based on the market forces of these funds. The emphasis on the existence of the loanable funds is focused also on vital view in a money-using environment, the largest amount of money typically resides in a consistent circulated wave. (Tsiang, 1989).

2.2.2 The Theory Shiftability

Under the shiftability theory a bank's liquidity can be calculated to the degree in which its assets can easily be transferred for good prices to other purchasers for cash. The banking law of 1935 now requires Federal Reserve Banks expressly to lend credit for appropriate assets to member banks. The old standard liquidity theory of short maturities was no longer the only basis on which banks would lend. The sound essence of the assets and their acceptability for the then Feds became new liquidity requirements, in which bank assets would now be passed to the Feds. This considerably widened possibility of asset change in an emergency undoubtedly gave some impetus to long-term bank lending. The issue of liquidity should be discussed in times especially as much as it is a changing issue is not a problem of matured loans. Once a bank can still obtain assistance from another in case of emergencies, there is no need to depend on mature loans. In fact, the way to achieve the minimum in reserve matters isn't about depending on maturity period but also by keeping a substantial amount of reserves that can be moved from one bank for another in exchange for cash. (Moulton, op. cit., p. 723)). Moulton further notes that "The liquidity is simply a matter of moving to the Federal Reserve banks under the Federal Reserve System. (Prochnow, 1949).

2.2.3 The Theory of Anticipated Income

An anticipated liquidity income theory is similar in some respects to traditional and shifting bank liquidity theories. A single banker can probably say that a well-managed and profitable bank institution will regularly make principal and interest payments on an adequately made term loan in good economic times. In times of distress, he can also reasonably presume, with a satisfactory report of his previous earnings, that the same controlled and developed business would be able to offer the same arrangement for payments on a long-term debt payment plan as a short-term debt. The efficient operation of the anticipated income theory of liquidity depends, From the entire banking system's perspective, the general consumption for the products and services generated by term-loan borrowers. No less so in relation to the liquidation process of the bank system's short-term loans. The traditional liquidity theory does not provide a predetermined threshold on possible credit expansion, nor does it provide for

predetermined limits on possible credit expansion in the anticipated income theory for cash including wider rediscount privileges currently in place at Federal Reserve banks. According to the anticipated income theory of liquidity, the borrower is under pressure to save, withdraw, or prolong the substitution of his credit to get the money he needs to liquidate the debt. (Prochnow, 1949)

2.2.4 The Theory of Liquidity Preference

This paper examined Keynes's theory of liquidity preferences to examine Keynes's continuing importance and application for the issues of the monetary theory and policy from the Treatise on Money to General Theory and beyond. Unlike the neoclassical understanding of "special case," Keynes considered his liquidity favored theory of interests as a substitute for faulty savings or creditworthiness fund theories of interest that emphasize actual productive forces and thrift. He argued that money, not saving, was the basic necessity for economic activity in the economies of monetary production. Thus, by transforming neoclassical awareness, "roosters" must be adjusted for by the real economy in terms of financing as described in the financial system. The biggest practical challenge is whether a deliberate monetary policy can be enforced to achieve meaningful results. In this context, Keynes's research provides insights into practical questions such as policy legitimacy and management of expectations, which go far beyond heterodox and endogenously monetary methods and Wicksellian theory, which continues to be caught in the illusion of financial Neutrality. (Bibow, 2005).

2.3 Determinants of Commercial Banks ' Financial Performance

Bank performance determinants can be listed in bank internal and external macroeconomic variables. Theoretical variables are used for the determination of output. Internal factors are the banking institutions attributes that affect banks' profitability. The administration and the committee's strategic decisions ultimately influence such factors. Factors that externally influence the profitability of banks are sectoral and nation-wide factors beyond the control of the Business. (Al-Tamimi, 2010; Aburime, 2008).

2.3.1 Liquidity Management

Liquidity management is the regular handling of investment in a company's existing assets, existing debt, short-term/quick borrowing, and short-term/quick surplus cash accumulation that influence the company's profitability. The effective control of all working capital elements is synonymous with existing assets and debts. (Pandey, 2010)

Accordingly, liquidity management requires the volume of investment in liquid assets in order to satisfy the short-term maturing obligations of creditors and others. As cash or almost cash reserves, liquidity has enough money to satisfy its financial obligations. Money is power in business, especially during difficult economic times or if the markets are unstable. Companies do not pay their bills or implement growth plans without cash, and it may be challenging to get credit or take advantage of market opportunities. A business which is unable to cover its current liabilities in due course and still refuses to comply with its obligations towards credit, commodities suppliers can be deemed incompetent or bankruptcy. (Panigrahi, 2013).

Liquidity management is similar to non-current asset management since a company relies in all cases on market risk analyzes for all of its assets in both situations. Liquidity management, however, varies from non-current asset management however is in threefold: firstly, the time frame enables the methods of reducing and combining essential in the budget of capital, which is not the instance in the case of existing asset administration; secondly, large cash and other existing capital volumes create a greater liquidity condition, but also decreases the ultimate liquidity position. This indicates that the management of liquid / current assets is more versatile than that of non-current assets. (Pandey, 2010)

2.3.2 Asset Quality

Asset quality includes an assessment of the company's assets to help quantify the credit risk level and size affiliated all of its service. This refers to both the left-side to the statement of financial position of a bank which reflects the value of loans which generate a bank's revenue. The standard of assets and loans are two terms that are practically synonymous, while its management by the financing industry is considered

highly critical. Under the (Basle, 1997) Banking Supervision Committee, the basic principles of efficient banking supervision included 25 key principles, seven of which were aimed at dealing with the relevant issues of value of bank assets and credit risk management. This meant that the standard of assets in every country of the world is of general interest to financial supervisors. (Abata, 2014).

The overall risk associated with the different assets held by individuals or entities was defined as the quality of assets also known as loan quality. (Ombaba, 2013). Lending that may be non-performing assets if the lender fails to meet repayment obligations, is the most common asset that needs strict determination of asset quality. Risk managers also measure asset quality by classifying each asset in numeric order, based on the level of risk. (Nzoka, 2015).

2.3.3 Macroeconomic Factors

The macroeconomic control variables are defined by profitability determinants. Inflation, long term interest rates or growth of monetary supply are also the factors that are usually used. Revell discusses the problem of the relationship between profitability and inflation (1979). According to him the effect of inflation on bank profitability tends to depend on whether banks' wage rates and other operating costs keep rising rapidly than the inflation. The issue should be how stable an economy is really in order to predict future inflation correctly and so that banks can control their operating costs accordingly. (Perry, 1992), in this vein, points out that the degree with which inflation influences profitability of banks varies depending on the optimum suspense of core inflation. The rate of inflation that even the financial institution fully ensures which banking institutions can change interest rates sufficiently to increase revenue increase revenue rapidly unlike their expenditures, while acquiring higher income. Most studies have shown that there was a strong correlation amid inflation growth, long-term interest rates and revenue growth. (e.g. ((Bourke, 1989), ((Molyneux & Thornton, 1992))).

2.3.4 Capital Adequacy

The Capital Adequacy can be used as an indicator of the financial strength and stability as a percentage ratio of primary capital of the assets i.e., loans and investments. Banks

are generally anticipated to absorb normal income losses. But unforeseen losses cannot be absorbed by ordinary earnings. Capital is used to mitigate the losses in these irregular cases. Capital thus plays the part of insurance. Suitable bank capital is a boost to confidence. It confides in the Bank 's continuing financial viability to the client, the public and the regulator. Trust to the creditor that his cash is secured; public confidence to the that it can or will continue to, truly take its credit and its bank requirements into account in ups and downs. Awareness that capital adequacy affects the viability of the financial sector is important not just for bank managers, but for many stakeholders including central banks, banking institutions, governments and others. (Olalekan & Adeyinka, 2013).

2.3.5 Management Efficiency

Efficiency in management is another way of measuring bank ' financial stability. It is connected to the management's ability to effectively utilize their resources and to increase their sales and lower production costs, which can be calculated by various financial relations or ratios. Thus, it is used to figure out whether a bank has more or fewer employees. It also tracks the bank productivity level to optimize employee benefit. (Palamalai & Saminathan, 2016). (Assfaw, 2018).

Efficiency in management is another key aspect of a CAMEL model, ensuring a bank's long - term survival. To better understand this, interest-free spending is factored in the form of the gross cost ratio, the net gains to total deposits and investment gains over total asset ratios. ((Ermias. 2016), (Assfaw, 2018)).

2.4 Empirical Review

(Babarinde et al, 2020). focusing on assessing the financial results of Nigeria's targeted deposit money banks (DMBs) from 2011-2017 in various forms of their impacts on the liquidity risk management. Data were collected for the period from the published accounts of 10 Deposit Money Bank's (DMBs) were collected using a post-facto research design. For data analysis, panel data regression was used. The costs of financing were inconsequentially positive for the return on assets. Interest coverage ratios have a major and detrimental relationship to asset returns. The capital adequacy ratio is nonetheless optimistic, but the provision of the loan loss indicates a negative

and negative relationship with the benefit. Furthermore, there is a negative effect of unperformed loans on the return of banks on assets. The results show that the liquidity risk (finance risk, interest Coverage ratio and unperformed loans) and the bank efficiency (ROA) are strongly and negatively linked. The DMB regulator should also be careful to raise a minimum liquidity ratio as this would have a negative impact on its financial results. Nigeria's DMBs could raise core capital because there was a positive and important financial output impact on capital adequacy

(Chen et al, 2018). The researchers aim to explore the variables for liquidity risk and thus the correlation for both the risk factors and performance of bank liquidity in 12 developed economies during the period 1994 to 2006. The liquidity risk factors are categorized even further into bank, supervision and market conditions for the model of liquidity risk. Also, by regression of fixed effects, the model is generated. As part of the model of liquidity risk and performance, an endogenous measure of financial performance is considered towards liquidity risk and the instruments table data regression variables are applied for this model. In addition, these factors of market structure, supervisory factors and macroeconomic conditions also affect bank performance, apart from liquidity risk. The findings suggest that the liquidity risk is the endogenous factor in determining for bank performance. The liquidity risk comprises liquidity elements and external funding dependency, supervision and legislative and macro - economic factors. In addition to liquidity, the contribution made by this report is to apply other liquidity risk measures.

(Cucinelli, 2013). Is trying to investigate the drivers of bank liquidity risk in the European area and this study was done between the period of 2006-2018. The sample consists of 1080 Eurozone banks listed and not listed and the methodology used is OLS regression based on panel data. The primary objective of this research is to examine how liquidity risks are related to the liquidity risks with liquidity coverage and a net stable financing ratio and certain particular variables in bank structure. The findings emphasize that liquidity risk management can have an impact on size, capitalization, asset quality and specialization. While not all the relationship with both liquidity measures is evident to the particular variables included in the analysis. The

research shows, in fact, that bigger banks with more lending specialization appear to have lower liquidity; it can all be attributed to banks' propensity to assume that in situations of difficulties they can turn to last resort lenders. Highly capitalized banks have greater long-term liquidity, whereas asset qualities banks are more vulnerable to short term liquidity. As far as the financial crisis is concerned, it just tends to affect the liquidity coverage ratio and hence the short-term control of liquidity. This could be attributable to banks becoming more focused on handling liquidity on a short horizon throughout the economic crisis. The expansion of the study, including banks from other countries, could boost future studies.

(Cornett et al, 2011) report that they examined the management of liquidity risk and the financial crunch credit supply. Due to the crash of interbank markets and the fall of asset-backed and loans-funded securities, liquidation at banks accelerated during the financial crisis of 2007–2009. The researchers explained in this article how this liquidity increase was dispersed through the banking system. They also found that more liquid asset portfolios, that is banks with more loans and securitized assets, raised their liquid asset holdings and reduced lending. The study also reveals how banks relies strongly on secure funding sources, i.e., fundamental deposits and capital, continued to all other banking institutions. In the form of undrawn credit obligations, the off-balance sheets liquidity risk, materialized when a creditor drew on vast sums of existing commitments. This removed the creditability and restricted the origination of new credit. according to the study findings, the researcher finds that liquidity risk exposure is the key reason why bank credit output has deteriorated at the height of the crisis. This suggested that attempts to resolve the banks liquidity crisis have triggered a decrease in lending.

(Charmler et al., 2018). The researchers aim to investigate dynamics and the liquidity effect in banks and the various impacts on commercial banks' performance in Ghana.

This research is focused primarily on panel regression analyses in a quantitative study. The analysis was obtained from a sample of 23 banks from 2010 to 2016 operating in Ghana. Data on all topics, objects, or institutions of the population are one of the

problems of a panel analysis connected with analyzing the entire population. In terms of financial profitability, total return assets and return-on-equity are calculated as a dependent model variable for this analysis. For the banks sampled for this study, the study used two liquidity measures. The first concerns the liquid asset ratio. This indicator is a liquidity indicator that is determined by dividing total cash assets into total assets. The bank liquid assets ratio are explained: easy to convert to real money. The ratio of liquid funds and total assets is calculated. It represents the average period/number of times the gross interest-bearing debt protected by liquid assets. In this analysis, the company's basic variables were net interest rates, asset quality, foreign investment, and bank size. The results of the regression and correlation tests clearly show that the liquidity and bank output are positively related. However, the correlation is very high for asset return compared with equity returns. Although the correlation was statistically small, cash assets were negative compared to capital income. The study suggests that if the banks are to increase their profitability, they have to look critically at their liquidity. The results suggested that there is a positive link to the profitability of banks between variables like the net interest income, the equity ratios, the banks size and foreign possession. The findings do have a range of consequences for the banking sector and its managers and the policymakers.

(Enekwe et al., 2017). The researchers investigate the influence of liquidity risk on Nigerian banks in the period 2009-2014. This research uses the ex- facto model as it entails past activities/events which cannot be manipulated. Six (6) variables were used in this paper: The net operating profit margin for Deposits, liquid assets, cash gaps, the (NPL) and the Independent (LEV). Using ordinary least squares technique, model estimation was performed. The study was focused on descriptive statistics, Spearman rating correlations and regression analyzes the findings indicate that the deposits, cash, and non-performing loans are linked to NOPM, whereas the liquidity and leverage ratios are negative in comparison to the (NOPM) which is the net operating profit margin of the chosen depository monetary financial institutions. Normally, the variance of the dependent variable within this study was caused by the variation of 94.24%. It also showed that deposits, cash, and loans do not make a success of (NOPM), although cash gaps and leverage do have little impact on the NOPM. The

study suggested that banks create the necessary cash for every product line and continue to maintain alternative threshold to decrease the cash balance level by making the product available to even more clients, and particularly low-income payers. Simultaneously banks should suggest engaging corporate customers that are able to hold a broad cash reserve for a lengthy period of time in their banks.

(İncekara & Çetinkaya, 2019). This research also focuses also on comparing the Islamic and conventional banking liquidity risk management framework in Turkey. The sample contains panel data analysis and involvement in Turkey for both 2014 and 2018 from conventional banks. The study included a record of 6 banking sectors functioning between 2014 and 2018 (3 participation and 3 conventional). In 2012-18, quarterly information was used to define factors that impact the liquidity risk, respectively to all Turkish Islamic and conventional banks. The analysis was therefore calculated by the regression method for the panel results. In the analysis, econometric models were found to be relevant at 99 % confidence level for both types of banking. These findings show that the variables selected could account for liquidity risk by 82% and Islamic banking by 42% for conventional banks. The conventional banks have shown independent factors in NPL and the liquid asset (LA), but in Islamic banks 4 variables are important. Non-performing/Failing loans (NPL), the liquid asset (LA), GDP and inflation were essential. (INF). It was optimistic and statistically significant in Islamic banking, with the NPL variable negatively, having 95% reliability and financial leverage in traditional Finance. This result shows that the rise in the overall loan volume to reduces the traditional banks and rises Islamic bank liquidity risk. The liquid asset (LA) variables were negative and statistically relevant in relation to a 99% trust in the bank's total assets and liquidity risk. In terms of the financial risks in the Islamic banking system, findings from the research reveals that the variables ROE and ROA had been irrelevant. Furthermore, the GDP and interest rates factors (INFs) were insignificant when describing liquidities risks in conventional currencies. It is very important for banks to have a strong liquidity framework not only for bank efficiency and financial system stability but also to prevent liquidity economic crisis.

(Kaitibi et al., 2017). The researchers focused on investigating the effect on the profitability and efficient credit management systems used by Sierra Leone commercial banks. The secondary data derived primarily on the Bank's five-year financial statements and its annual reports for 2010–1998. The data were evaluated both quantitatively and qualitatively using the ratios and charts. The credit management findings has performance has a big impact on the financial performance of banking sector in Sierra Leone. Likewise, Rokel Commercial Bank has leadership qualities that seem to support Rokel Bank's future performance. The optional branch network, credit options, and staff strengths were the factors which Rokel Commercial Bank Ltd has considered in its credit risk management. Priority should be given to sectors of the economy contributing more often to economic development. The overall recommendation of the Bank in terms of its effectiveness in credit management would be that loans be efficient low-capital tasks and enterprises priority. Similarly, unperforming credits should be curtailed and the production of advancements without can profitability / revenue. The results from this study suggested that in order to increase its profitability, banks in Sierra Leone needed a good credit policy.

(Musiega et al., 2017) Analyze the liquidity risk impacts on the efficiency of commercial banks in Kenya. This study was done during the year 2006-2015 despite stability and resilience of the banking sector, two non-systemic banks, which was attributed to liquidity risk, were placed in receivership by the Kenyan Central Bank. Kenya's target population was 44 trade banks (CBK, 2015). Two thirds of financial sector assets are accounted for. Secondary sources of data were collected for financial statements from the Kenyan central bank and various bank databases from 2006 to 2015. The results used e-views software to calculate the liquidity-risk from liquid assets-to-total asset ratio had a strong and important performance relation Descriptive, correlating analysis, and random and fixed impacts were used. The panel data correlation values for total assets liquid assets (DLQ1) and liquid assets (DLQ 2) were extremely low, suggesting that the liquidity risk values are not multicollinear. The regression results for asset return (DROA) with the liquidity risk calculation that liquid assets to overall deposits (DLQ2) in their optimal equation were not important. Banking institutions should identify the key factors influencing their ability to obtain

capital and carefully track the factors to ensure sound liquidity. Commercial banks should have an oversight structure which would allow them to evaluate liquidity-risk and liquidity of banks both in normal times and during stressful periods.

In this research the final objective of Musembi (2018) was also to assess financial results of listed commercial banks on the Nairobi Stock Exchange the effects of the liquidity risk determinants. A descriptive approach is used in the analysis. The target group included 11 commercial banks selected for Nairobi Stock Exchange 2011-2015. Qualitative and quantitative methods have been used in the analysis. A main data collection questionnaire was being used. A sample of 42 members of the Asset and Responsibility Management Committee was selected. Secondary information of the Central Bank of Kenya annual report has been used. The study revealed that the level of liquidity has had a beneficial impact on commercial banks' return on assets (ROA), although this has little impact. Data have been analyzed in compliance with the study objectives of the multiple regression methodology. The connection for both liquidity risk determinant and financial results was evaluated using correlation analysis. Asset quality has been found to have a major positive impact on asset returns for Nairobi Securities Exchange-selected commercial banks. The researcher also found that the inflation significantly negatively impacts banking institutions mentioned on the securities exchange in Nairobi on their return on assets. The research found that the degree of liquidity had a beneficial effect on the financial effectiveness of selected banks, but did not also have a substantial impact. It concluded also that the financial efficiency of selected commercial banking institutions is influenced positively and considerably by capital adequacy. The study recommends that commercial banking institutions with a stock exchange in Nairobi should seek to improve financial performance, define and maintain an optimum level of liquidity in order to boost their financial performance. Selected banks should raise core capital because capital adequacy has been shown to influence their performance in a positive way. In addition, the analysis indicates that commercial Banking institutions contract goods of high-quality asset should be preserved, particularly loan portfolio, and strategies for protecting against high inflation rates and inflation volatility should be established as well.

(Maaka, 2013) aimed to create the liquidity risk connection with financial results of commercial banks in Kenya. During 2008–2012, the report followed a correlation analysis concept that gathered data from 33 banks' accounts, income statements and notes. The findings of the report indicated that Kenya's commercial bank is with negative result because liquidity and leverage have been rising. Banks might have to lend much higher on the repo market, thus raising banks' costs with a significant liquidity space. The repo borrowing would assist the banks in keeping the negative effect of the Liquidity Gap within a reasonable Central Bank range. It can be inferred from this finding the detrimental effects of liquidity on commercial banks are prevented by retaining adequate cash reserves. The findings therefore indicate that a bank successful liquidity management level of effectiveness would affect and will negatively associated with most of the variables commonly used to affect the profitability of a business with a conventional liquidity management company. The study shows certain policy effects in the country for managers and prospective investors. The Kenyan profitability level of commercial banks is influenced by the deposit volumes by the customer and also by cash. Banks can expand their client income stream by designing a product more available for consumers and particularly low-income customers, who have long been overlooked by major banks. Also, banks should consider engaging large companies who are ready to hold a substantial bank cash base for a longer period of time. Additional studies may provide a wider view of success and economic factors as well.

(Rudhani & Balaj, 2019). The research seeks to analyze the control of liquidity by using liquidity risk measures for Kosovo's commercial banks between 2008 and 2017. This study uses qualitative methods that put together the empirical analysis and quantitative analyzes of different scholars. The report further assesses the liquidity risk control status of commercial banking sectors in Kosovo using the comparative methodology of the submitted data and review of the findings presented in the report and compare them to the quality standards in the control of liquidity risk. In Kosovo, the banking institutions remains highly sustainable and stable at the financial level. Liquidity and liquidity risk tend to be two essential components of the banking

institutions reliability. The key source of funding for the company of a bank were mainly deposits, at very low levels of loans between commercial banks and other instruments of debt. Moreover, the exposure to liquidity risks during the crisis was limited due to this funding model. The liquidity reserves in the Kosovo commercial banks were higher than the amount needed for CBK from 2008 to 2018. Liquidity risk management is a bank 's duty and therefore recommends that the bank develop a strong liquidity risk management system, including a high-quality liquid asset (BCBS, 2008) to preserve liquidity at an acceptable level;

2.5 Conceptual framework

Figure 2.1: The diagram of the response and predictor parameters is shown in below:

2.6 Summary

The impact of liquidity management on financial performances have been drawn from the various empirical research both in Sierra Leone and beyond. The findings suggest the liquidity vulnerability is the inherent determiner of bank efficiency. The report mentioned that if the profitability of the banks is to increase, they have to look critically at their liquidity aspects. The effect on banks' financial results of liquidity risk control is a controversial topic requiring further investigation from the respective positions of different theories and the findings of empiric studies.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This section describes the analysis method being used in this thesis to analyze variables associations by the researcher to investigate the associations of variables. The chapter covers the research preparation/research design, study population, data sources, data analysis methods, diagnostic tests, and empirical model.

3.2 Research Design

This chapter deals with a descriptive research method. The design of the research is a strategy for collecting, measuring, and analyzing data generated to address your research query (Sekaran & Bougie, 2011).

The descriptive design of research also helps to reveal connections and to determine the relationship between predetermined variables through deep evaluation.

The key feature of this approach is that the researcher is unable to monitor the variables; the study can report only what happened and what is going on. This could include quantitative sets of information viewed in numerical form along a spectrum, such as test scores.

3.3 Population

The population involved in the study was the banking institutions in Sierra Leone and Kenya. The research-based on 35 banking institutions in Sierra Leone and Kenya offering financial services for 10 years period from 2009-2018. The research units were intentionally sampled to ensure the availability of financial data during the 2009-2018 study period. The sample size was therefore produced by 25 commercial banks have been in service throughout this period studied. (Appendices I & II). These countries are chosen because both have standard and common banking practices that mostly contribute to ensuring banking performance. (BSL Annual report, 2017). (Bank Supervision Report, 2013).

3.4 Data Collection

In the annual publications by the financial institution of Sierra Leone and Kenya, the researchers used secondary data.

The study was performed out with secondary data sources from the annual reports and accounts released (statement of financial position and income statement) obtained from the central bank and the separate bank websites of Sierra Leone and Kenya for the year 2009-2018. (bsl.gov.sl/Publications.html), (centralbank.go.ke/reports/cbk-reports-and-financial-statements/) (africanfinancials.com/company/ke-kcb/). The details on the annual net profits, overall assets, total deposits, total liabilities, equity, total quick assets, total income, and annual operating expenses gathered from the respective financial statements on the accounts of the banks reviewed. Related data have also been gathered from banks' websites to ensure that there are representative data there for the analysis. The sampling period between 2009-2018 was chosen because there were a huge asset base and a wide variety of commercial bank operations. The research also seeks to analyze the influence of the recent financial recession on liquidity risk management.

3.5 Data Analysis

This study uses panelized multiple regression models using generalized moments methods (GMM). The study explores the relationship seen between liquidity risk management and financial returns for different banking institutions using the GMM estimation method established by (Arellano & Bover, 1995) and (Blundell & Bond, 2000). Multiple regressions use two or more independent, linear relations to explain the change during a variable. (Allen, 1997). (Uyanık & Güler, 2013) defines regression analysis as a technique of analyzing the relation between variables of reason and outcomes.

3.5.1 Diagnostic Test

Diagnostics is a part of the regression analysis which aims at investigating whether the calculated model and the assumptions that we made about the data and model match the data collected. (Baldrich, 2019).

3.5.2 Empirical Model Estimation

The study investigates the liquidity risk management impact on the commercial banks' financial performance of Sierra Leone and Kenya. For this reason, the study follows the previous literature using two simultaneous equations. (Ben Naceur & Kandil., 2009), (Zheng et al, 2018), (Agoraki et al., 2011), (Fiordelisi & al.,2011), (Hussain et Hassan, 2005), (Lee & Hsieh, 2013), (Vollmer & Wiese) and this is the following:

$$P_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1.1)$$

$$R_{it} = K_0 + K_1 R_{it-1} + K_2 LATA_{it} + K_3 LDR_{it} + K_4 LRMR_{it} + K_5 CAR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$$

In the above two equations described, the subscript *i* signifies the cross-sectional aspect of the various banks, and *t* indicates the time and the ε_{it} shows the standard error term including the unnoticed bank-specific effect and the unusual error.

The first equation is used to measure commercial banks' performance and the dependent profitability variable is therefore determined by the return on Assets (ROA). P_{it} shows performance of bank with the ROA-before tax in the equation and the β_0 refers to the constant term. The P_{it-1} refers to the period of one lagged performance variable, while K_1 is the coefficient

The Second equation test the liquidity risk management of the banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya from 2009 to 2018. R_{it} and the P_{it} shows the meaning relating to the first equation; K_0 is the constant term and R_{it-1} refers to the period of one lagged performance variable while K_1 is the coefficient. The independent variables of liquidity are classified as LATA, LDR, Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR), and Capital Adequacy (CAR) ratios.

Where:

Dependent variable (ROA) -Financial Performance

(ROA) = Profit Before Tax/Average Asset **ε_{it}** = Random Error

Independent Variable:

β_0 = Constant

(LATA) = Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset

= Liquid Asset/Total Asset

β_1, K_1 , = coefficient

(LDR) = Loan- To -Deposit Ratio = Total Loans/Deposit **t** = Time

(LRMR)= Liquidity Risk Management Ratio/Debt Ratio = Total Liabilities / Total Asset

(CAR)= Capital Adequacy ratio =Equity/Total Asset

The panel data analysis was performed using both descriptive and statistical techniques for this report. A panel data estimation approach is implemented since the data provides information on cross-sectional units observed over time.

The software E-View version 9 has been used to produce descriptive and statistics for multiple regression models using generalized moments methods (GMM). The study explores in evaluating the relationship between liquidity risk management and financial returns for different banking institutions using the GMM estimation method provided by (Arellano & Bover, 1995) and (Blundell & Bond, 2000). The GMM estimation method adapted here because there were issues with the simultaneous equations, such as the issue of endogeneity, serial correlation, and heteroscedasticity.

To perform the regression with Eviews-9 using GMM, the study first checks if the equation is overidentified or not, as it is one of the criteria for the use of GMM. The analysis also investigates whether Endogeneity, serial correlation, and heteroscedasticity problems are encountered in the models of each equation. The research utilizes the Durbin–Wu–Hausman endogeneities test and the white heteroscedastic test to assess these problems. The analysis also identifies that the Hausman fixed/random effects test shows the model is adequate.

This study involves descriptive statistics including mean, median, minimum, maximum, and standard deviations in terms of explaining the depth of research

variables. The Pearson correlation shows that there were no multicollinearity problems with the study variables.

Finally, by implementing GMMs, this study carried out robustness tests to support findings of whether or not the results are consistent.

3.5.3 Significance of Statistical Tests

The coefficient determinant (R^2 value) was used to demonstrate the difference in the output variable, which is effectively affected by the predictor variables. The R-Square tells how much variables that the explanatory variables may describe.

The Durbin-Watson Statistics is testing the first order autocorrelation problem in the error term. And the rule says that, if the Durbin-Watson is less than 2 then it will indicate evidences of a positive serial correlation of the model. And if the the Durbin-Watson statistics is greater than 2 then there is negative autocorrelation. Also, if the fellow of Durbin-Watson is 2 then there will be no autocorrelation.

CHAPTER 4

DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This section covers the data analysis, results and discussions of the study. The findings are centered on an overview of 35 financial banking institutions in Sierra Leone and Kenya over a 10-year period (2009- 2018). Panelized multiple regression models have been established using Generalized Moments Methods (GMM). The impact on financial performance in commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya of liquidity risk management investigation. This section discusses the findings of the regression analysis and the descriptive findings, and the findings discussion will then be held.

4.2 The Rate of Response

For the period 2009 to 2018, annual reports were collected from 25 commercial banks. No financial statements were available for, Skye Bank (SL)Ltd, National Development Bank (SL) Ltd, Zenith Bank (SL)Ltd, International Commercial Bank (SL)Ltd, First International Bank (SL)Ltd, Keystone Bank (SL) Ltd, First Community Bank Ltd Kenya, Charterhouse Kenyan Bank Limited, Middle East Bank of Kenya Ltd, Equatorial Bank of Kenya limited and Gulf African Bank Ltd. 88% of the available data is considered relatively high.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis

The following table signifies the outcome of the descriptive statistics of the regression model's outcome and predictor variables. The model contains the banks' variables that have been tested.

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	LATA	LDR	LRMR	CAR
Mean	0.048107	0.258923	0.653779	0.767110	0.187943
Median	0.033328	0.206751	0.703331	0.843967	0.152446
Maximum	0.699684	0.920222	0.997607	0.999729	1.410413
Minimum	0.000295	5.60E-05	0.000486	0.002332	0.000154
Std. Dev.	0.079905	0.220883	0.234963	0.256411	0.194831
Skewness	5.389066	1.091222	-0.882034	-2.328019	3.773131
Kurtosis	36.37483	3.632059	3.217588	6.978492	17.70928
Jarque-Bera	12812.99	53.77662	32.90919	390.6989	2846.967
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	12.02673	64.73074	163.4446	191.7774	46.98571
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.589812	12.14857	13.74674	16.37087	9.451847
Observations	250	250	250	250	250

Note: Author Calculation

The descriptive statistics from the above table show that for the period of analysis, the mean return on assets was 0.048107 and with a 0.079905 standard deviation, which means that the return on asset (ROA) values were low in terms of the time provided lower standard deviation. For ROA, the values of minimum and maximum are 0.000295 and 0.699684 and median values were 0.033328 respectively. The ROA is clearly leptokurtic looking at the kurtosis value $36.3 > 3$ and it has a positive skewness. The Jarque-Bera statistics for ROA are 12812.99 and below the Jarque-Bera statistics is the respective probability values and we clearly reject the distribution of the null hypothesis of the normal distribution for ROA because the probability value is highly statistically significant. This distribution is clearly not normal.

The LATA mean and median values were 0.258923 and 0.206751 respectively. The S.D of the LATA was 0.220883, which further indicates a lower variability in value over time, with a median of 0.920222 and a minimum of 5.60E-05. The LATA has a long right tail indicating a positive skewness it has a kurtosis value of $3.6 > 3$ indicating

that is leptokurtic. The Jarque-bera statistics for LATA are 53.77662 and below the Jarque-bera statistics is the probability values. We clearly reject the distribution of the null hypothesis of the normal distribution for LATA and mainly because the probability value is highly statistically significant.

Findings further showed that Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR) mean and median values are 0.653779 and 0.703331 respectively. The standard deviation is 0.234963, which is also an indicator of the lower volatility of the loan-to-deposit value. The minimum and maximum value of the deposit loan was 0.000486 and 0.997607, accordingly. This variable LDR mirrors a negative skewness and it is also mesokurtic because of the kurtosis value is $3.2=3$. The LDR Jarque-bera statistics are 32,90919 and the probability values are below the Jarque-bera statistics. We explicitly reject the distribution of the null hypothesis of the normal distribution for LDR, primarily because the probability value is highly significant.

The table above show that the mean liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR) for the study period was 0,767110. This means that the LRMR values were of low time variability as shown by the lower standard deviation. For this period, the standard deviation is 0,256411. For the LRMRs, the minimum and maximum values were 0.002332 and 0.999729, and the median values were 0.843967, respectively. The LRMR mirrors a negative skewness or has left tail and lower value than the sample mean and it is clearly leptokurtic as the kurtosis valve is greater than 3 ($6.97>3$). There are 390,6989 statistics for LRMR Jarque-bera, and the probability values are under Jarque-bera. We specifically reject the distribution of the null distribution hypothesis for LRMR mainly due to the high significant probability value.

Finally, findings indicate that the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) was 0.187943 on mean and 0.152446 on median. Its standard deviation from 0.194831 was 0.000154 and 1.410413 respectively, with minimum and maximum values. The CAR mirrors the skewness is positive and this implies that this distribution has a long right tail and higher than simple mean. The kurtosis value leptokurtic with ($17.7>3$). There are 2846,967 capital adequacy ratio (CAR) Jarque-bera statistics, and Jarque-bera is the

probability value. We explicitly reject the distribution of the zero-distribution ratio (CAR) hypothesis mainly because of the high significant probability value.

4.4 Correlation Analysis

The table below illustrates the coefficients of correlation derived from the data collected from the study's target population. Multicollinearity is also calculated by the table.

Table 4.2: Correlations

	ROA	LATA	LDR	LRMR	CAR
ROA	1.000000	-0.071997	0.141369	-0.145861	0.310725
LATA	-0.071997	1.000000	-0.312569	0.266528	-0.188529
LDR	0.141369	-0.312569	1.000000	-0.216880	0.295396
LRMR	-0.145861	0.266528	-0.216880	1.000000	-0.547161
CAR	0.310725	-0.188529	0.295396	-0.547161	1.000000

Note: Correlation is significant at the 1%,5%, 10% level

Note: Author Calculation

From the table above, we conclude that LATA and the LRMR has a negative correlation with the dependent variable ROA, Moreover, there is a positive correlation between other independent variables such as; LDR and CAR.

The figure above shows the association between the variables predictor and expected. The table shows the coefficients of correlations of LATA, and of LDR ratio, negative ($r = -0.31$) and 5% significant, and this means that an increase in or decrease of liquid assets to total assets will be followed by a loan-to-deposit increase or decrease.

Moreover, the results showed that the LATA and LRMR was positive ($r = 0.27$) and 5% significant. In contrast, this means that an increase or decrease LATA is followed by an increase or decrease in the LRMR between the total liabilities and the total asset.

The correlation between the LDR and the LRMR relationship (total liabilities to total assets) is negative value of -0.22 and is considered 5% significant, which suggests that an increase or decrease in the loan-to-deposit ratio will be followed by a decrease or increase in the LRMR relationship.

Finally, the correlation between the LRMR and the CAR relationship ($r=-0.55$) is significantly negative at 5%, which also implies that an increase or decrease in the correlation between LRMR will be followed by an increase or decrease in the capital adequacy ratio.

According to the correlation table above, among the two variables ROA and CAR shows the highest correlation with a positive value $r= 0.31$. Being that this correlation is not above 0.8 then it states that the correlation is not strong and which can suggest a nonexistence multicollinearity problem.

Multicollinearity does not present any problems with the variables used in the study, provided that the predictor coefficients are less than 0.8.

4.5 Hausman Test

The Hausman test statistic is a translation of the difference between both the estimation of fixed effect parameters and the estimation of random effects, which becomes asymptotically Chi-Sq. Statistic expressed under the null hypothesis. For these studies, values were differed to ensure the data was static but a Hausman test was used before regression to decide whether the goals for this analysis were to be evaluated using random effects or fixed effects model.

It is only the outcome of the Hausman Test that would give us the rightful estimate to apply in this model. When the P-value from the Hausman test is statistically significant, that means we are going to reject the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative. Rejecting the null hypothesis implies that the fixed effect of the estimator would be applied to this model.

Table 4.3: - Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq.		
	Chi-Sq.	Statistic	d.f. Prob.
Cross-section random	37.134829	5	0.0000

Note: level of Significance 5%

The Hausman test is presented as a 5-degree chi-square. From table above indicates the chi-sq statistics is 37.13 and the probability value is highly statistically significant i.e., it is less than 0.05. So, from this result we are rejecting the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative (fixed effect).

4.6 Panelized Multiple Regression Model

Table 4.4: The GMM Model Estimations

V	Coeff	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-2.821342	0.790789	-3.567758	0.0005
LOG (ROA (-1))	0.074406	0.103807	0.716777	0.4744
LOG(LATA)	0.867100	0.319401	2.714772	0.0073
LOG(LDR)	-0.399164	0.181814	-2.195451	0.0294
LOG(LRMR)	-1.065769	0.309854	-3.439587	0.0007
LOG(CAR)	-0.147309	0.472675	-0.311650	0.7557

Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
Period fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.267147	Mean dependent var	-3.619851	
Adjusted R-squared	0.122144	S.D. dependent var	1.134151	
S.E. of regression	1.062631	Sum squared resid	211.1574	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.473129	J-statistic	77.48688	
Instrument rank	39	Prob(J-statistic)	0.000000	

Significance at the 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Author Sources: 2021

Fixed effects are used for both period and cross-section therefore model controls for firm and year effects.

The Lagged values of variables are included as methods to minimize the endogeneity problem.

According to the outcome of the fixed effect Model, close observation of the coefficient reveals that the Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA), Loan- To -Deposit Ratio (LDR) and Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) are the only statistically significant coefficients when using the fixed effect.

From the above table, one thing about the effect model is that the lagging dependent variable coefficient is seen as the upper bound. And in the fixed effect model it is seen as the lower bound. The interpretation of this effect is that the parameter of the coefficient is 0.074406 and this is indicating a lower bound fixed effect.

Firstly, from the table above we can see that the P-value for Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA) is 0.0073 and this indicates that the probability value is less than 0.05 and this means the LATA variable determines the dependent variable in a good way. So, Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA) is a significant independent variable for this regression model.

Secondly, the table above suggests that we can have the P-value for LDR variable at 0.0294, indicating that the LDR variable is good at evaluating the dependent variable with a p-value lower than 0.05. Therefore, for this regression model Loan- To -Deposit Ratio (LDR) is a significant independent variable.

Moreover, the above table describes that the P-value of Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) is 0.0007 and this shows that the probability value is less than 0.05 and this implies that the Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) variable is a strong determination of the dependent variable. Therefore, for this regression model Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) is a significant independent variable.

Finally, the probability figure for CAR is 0.7557 which is greater than 0.05. So, Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is not a significant independent variable for this regression model or Capital asset ratio (CAR) doesn't determine the dependent variable Return on Asset (ROA) in a good way.

The R-Square tells how much variables that the explanatory variables can describe. This indicates that all the independents' variables explained 26.7% of the dependent variable that is the Return on Asset (ROA). On the other hand, if we consider the Adjusted R-Square, then we can say the independent variables cumulatively determines 12.2% of the dependent variable. The more the adjusted R² or follow R², the more fit the model.

The Dubin-Watson Statistics is testing the autocorrelation problem in the error term. And the rule says that, if the Dubin-Watson is less than 2 then it will indicate evidences of a positive serial correlation of the model. With these statistics we can determine whether your dataset has autocorrelation or not. In this model, the Dubin-Watson statistics is 1.473129 showing that the dataset has a positive autocorrelation mainly because the Dubin-watson is less than 2. This is showing that there is autocorrelational problem. Even though the model is good one according to the R² and the adjusted R² but the Dubin-Watson statistics model is saying that the data of this model has autocorrelation problem.

4.7 Discussion of the Findings

The R² value results suggested a disparity in the ROA and as a result of adjustments in the ratio of liquid assets to total assets, loan-to-deposit ratio, liquidity risk management ratio, and capital asset ratio. As shown below, the resulting equation observed that the increased liquidity procedures negatively affect the financial result of commercial banks.

Empirical Model Estimation was:

$$P_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 P_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1.1)$$

$$R_{it} = K_0 + K_1 R_{it-1} + K_2 LATA_{it} + K_3 LDR_{it} + K_4 LRMR_{it} + K_5 CAR_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2.1)$$

The above estimation was model as:

$$P_{it} = -2.82 + 0.074 + 0.790$$

$$R_{it} = -2.82 + 0.074 + 0.867 - 0.399 - 1.065 - 0.147 + 0.790$$

Liquidity risk management (LRMR), with a 106.5 % liquidity effect, means that financial performance has been negatively affected by the LRMR by 106.5%. An increase in LRMR by banks attributed to a 106.5% decrease in return on asset.

The outcomes of the GMM estimate are therefore correct. It can be concluded that liquidity determines bank profitability significantly. In particular, profitability (ROA) is negatively affected by LATA ($\beta = 0.867$) at the 1% significance level, while LDR ($\beta = -0.399$) at the 5% significance level is positively affected. In addition, at the 1% level of significance, Performance (ROA) is negatively impacted by the independence variable LATA ($\beta = -1,065$). Furthermore, findings reveals that the control variable CAR ($\beta = -0.147$) at the 5% stage is statistically insignificant to the profitability/performance ratio (ROA) of the bank.

An important inverse relationship is signified by the (LATA) and (ROA) coefficient. Coefficient was 0.867 and the p-value was 0.0073, which was 5% significant and 95% trust. Negative correlation means rise in the liquid assets to total assets over the observation period will result in a decrease in the return on assets. This indicates that the probability value is less than 0.05 and this mean the variable LATA determines the dependent variable in a good way. So, Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA) is significant independent variable for this regression mode.

The table 4.6 above indicates the LDR coefficient was -0.399 and P-value, which is 0.0294, and the LDR variable is useful for measuring the reliable variable, which shows that this is less than 0.05, respectively. This regression mode has a significant independent variable Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR).

The table above also shows the coefficient of -1.065 and indicates that the P value in the liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR) is 0.0007 and shows the likelihood value below 0.05, which means a good determination of the dependent variable in liquidity

risk management ratio (LRMR). This regression mode is also subject to significant independent variable of the liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR). And then, for Capital Asset Ratio (CAR) the coefficient is -0.147 and the probability value is 0.7557 and exceeds 0.05. The capital asset ratio (CAR) for this regression model is either not a relevant independent variable or the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) does not correctly define the dependent asset return variable (ROA).

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter summarizes and gives recommendations derived in the conduct of the study in evaluating the liquidity risk management impact on commercial bank's financial performance of Sierra Leone and Kenya.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

This research aims towards investigating the relation between the liquidity risk management and the banking institutions financial performance, taking into consideration Sierra Leone and Kenya. The research concentrates on 25 commercial banks and the design of the descriptive study was adopted. Secondary data have been collected for 10 years between 2009 and 2018. A descriptive statistical analysis and panelized multiple regression models using the GMM method that assesses the relationship regarding liquidity risk management and commercial banks' financial results, taking into account Sierra Leone and Kenya.

The findings of this study were summarized according to the statement of the problems stated in chapter one (1) and the literature review.

This study aims to understand the problem relating to the link between liquidity risk management and financial performance from Sierra Leone and Kenya financial institution?

According to the various studies from the different researchers, there was a great deal to develop the link that exist between liquidity risk management practice and banks' financial results. The analysis including its scope, methodology, time, and background vary and the corresponding findings indicate there had been a complicated connection between liquidity risk management and financial result. from Sierra Leone and Kenya.

In the findings of (Bwacha & Xi, 2018), Different hypotheses and empirical findings have tried to explain the said relationship that exists between liquidity risk management and the banks financial performance to boost sound and robust financial

systems. The theory of shifting capacity asserts that banks are not only important for growing liquidity but are also in a stronger position to fulfill their economic obligations to preserve their ability to hold assets that can be transferred easily without delay and substantial losses.

The control of liquidity risks is synonymous with uncertainty as all other factors that can affect the financial achievement of banking institutions. (Kumar, 2012) asserts in a highly competitive market environment that liquidity risk management and profitability is a crucial problem. He also claimed that income and liquidity are inverses. Increasing net assets would reduce profitability. (Boedeleau & Graham, 2010) warned that the retention of liquid assets would reduce the financial capacity of the banks beyond that stage.

(Chen et al, 2018) findings suggest that the endogenous factor in liquidity risk is determinant of bank performance. The liquidity risk comprises liquidity elements and external funding dependency, supervision, and legislative and macroeconomic factors. In addition to liquidity, the contribution made by this report is to apply other liquidity risk measures.

(Cucinelli. 2013) findings emphasize that liquidity risk management can have an impact on the scale, capitalization, asset quality, and specialization. The research shows that bigger banks with more lending specialization appear to have lower liquidity; it can all be attributed to banks' propensity to assume that in situations of difficulties they can turn to last resort lenders. Highly capitalized banks have greater long-term liquidity, whereas the banking sectors with better asset qualities are more vulnerable to short term liquidity. As far as the financial crisis is concerned, it just tends to affect liquidity coverage ratio and hence the short-term control of liquidity. This could be attributable to banks becoming more focused on handling liquidity on a short horizon in times of financial crisis. The expansion of the study, including banks from other countries, could boost future studies.

(Charmler et al., 2018) study suggest that if the banks are to increase their profitability, they have to look critically at their liquidity. The results suggested that there is a positive link to the profitability of banks between variables like the net interest income,

the equity ratios, the banks size, and foreign possession. The findings do have a range of consequences for the banking sector and its managers and policymakers.

In this study, (Musembi, 2018) research found that the degree of liquidity had a beneficial outcome on the financial efficiency of selected banks, but did not also have a substantial impact. It concluded also that the financial efficiency of selected commercial banking institutions is influenced positively and considerably by the capital adequacy.

The regression model established for the period under study was:

$$P_{it} = -2.82 + 0.074 + 0.790 \dots\dots\dots(1.1)$$

$$R_{it} = -2.82 + 0.074 + 0.867 - 0.399 - 1.065 - 0.147 + 0.790 \dots\dots\dots(2.1)$$

The regression analysis shows that management liquidity risk and the commercial financial performance has a significant negative relationship. The study findings have shown how there an increase on (LATA) and also decreases the return on asset (ROA) by about 1%. The loan to deposit ratio (LDR) is increase and a subsequent decrease in the return on Asset (ROA) by 39.9%. There is increase in the Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) total liabilities to the total asset and will results in a relative decrease of -1.065 in the return on assets. At last, the control variable which was capital adequacy ratio (CAR) shows whereby an increase in the equity-to-total asset will result -0.147 decrease in return on assets (ROA).

Furthermore, an important inverse relationship is signified through the coefficient of LATA and return on assets (ROA). The coefficient was 0.867 and the p-value was 0.0073, which was 5% significant and 95% trust. A negative correlation means the LATA is increase over the observation period and the outcome will decrease the return on assets. This indicates that the probability value is less than 0.05 and this means the variable Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA) determines the dependent variable in a good way. So, Liquid Asset -to-Total Asset (LATA) is a significant variable for this regression model.

The panelized multiple regression model reveals that the loan to deposit ratio (LDR) probability value is P, which is 0.0294, and the LDR variable is useful for measuring the reliable variable, and it is less than 0.05, respectively. This regression model has a significant independent variable Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR).

Lastly, the panelized multiple regression model also indicates that the P-value in the liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR) is 0.0007 and shows the likelihood value below 0.05, which means a good determination of the dependent variable in liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR). This regression model is also subject to a significant independent variable liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR). And then, for Capital Asset Ratio (CAR), the probability value is 0.7557 and exceeds 0.05. The capital asset ratio (CAR) for this regression model is either not a relevant independent variable or the capital asset ratio (CAR) does not correctly define the dependent asset return variable (ROA).

The thesis seeks to evaluate the impact on the financial performance of commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya and their liquidity risk management. This study had based on 25 banking institutions and the design of the descriptive study was followed. Secondary data for 10 years from 2009 to 2018 yielding 250 observations of the bank-year have been obtained. A panel analysis was undertaken to assess the relation amid liquidity risk management and commercial banks' financial returns in Sierra Leone and Kenya. Commercial Bank variables here include return on asset, liquid asset-to-total asset, loan-to-deposit ratio, liquidity risk management ratio, and the capital adequacy ratio.

The analysis of the regression discloses that the liquidity risk management of financial results of commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya is significantly negatively related. The studies found that liquidity risk management accounted for 26.7% of the difference in return on the asset over the study period. The LATA, LDR, and total liabilities to total assets account for a substantial increase, led by total revenues.

5.3 Recommendation

The study developed an adverse relation regarding the management of liquidity risks and financial returns of Sierra Leone and Kenyan commercial banks, making it important to Management not only to improve the practice of effective liquidity management by maximizing return on asset (ROA) but also to put banks on a sound foundation to withstand risks that might arise in financial matters.

In the study findings the Loan-to-Deposit Ratio had a negative relationship with asset ratio throughout the period studied, making it necessary for the management of the banking sector in Sierra Leone and Kenya to pay close attention to how loan portfolios can optimize returns. To provide loans and progress and well-diversified portfolios, a reliable source of finance should be used to safeguard risks and optimize returns at the same time.

Further findings from this study had been that the LATA negatively affects the commercial bank's financial performance. It also indicates how banks must therefore be ensuring that they retain an optimum liquid asset amount that usually provide lesser returns while at the same time being able to satisfy customer requirements.

5.4 The Study Limitations

This study is based on commercial banks operating in Sierra Leone and Kenya. Accordingly, the research might well be limited by that of the study population that focused solely on Sierra Leone and Kenya. The meanings should thus be restricted to commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya and must not be applied to other countries because they had a various operational framework than Sierra Leone and Kenya. Factors in various countries such as crises can entail diverse liquidity risk management decisions.

The research was also focused primarily on commercial banks' financial outcomes and thus the financial effect of liquidity risk management was biased. When decisions on liquidity risk management are examined, some other considerations are to be regarded. Solvency is among the main factors. Hence, commercial banks must also be mindful of every other solvency risks

The research-based on a particular ten-year period (2009-2018). During this period, the operational environment can vary from other times, such as war, economic boom, or other economic shocks. Therefore, outcomes can differ if such disruptions occur to the economy so in this case decisions surrounding liquidity risk management could be different for commercial banks.

5.5 Suggestions for further research

Additional studies aimed to all banking institution for a long time can also be carried out to give the subject a larger perspective and contribute to the existence of expertise. For all economic sectors, liquidity management is essential. The analysis is based however solely on sample groups of Sierra Leone and Kenya commercial banks. It is essential to validate this research in other sectors that take more time study periods into account.

Further research on the impact of liquidity risk management can be carried out based on the product mixture of funding sources and investment. In this scenario, the analysis aims to determine how the funding mix defines the liquid assets needed and the effect on performance in the end. For instance, any commercial bank having a significant funding component in calling accounts has a large funding component in fixed accounts.

After that, more research could be carried out towards the impact of investment portfolio risk of commercial banks' financial performance and how this impacts the judgment on liquidity risk management. For instance, when financing for such liquid assets, including fixed treasury bills, comes from outlets whose costs are adjustable, the risk would be that a commercial bank might lose liquid assets in an increasing interest system.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

The study findings reveals that that liquidity risk management in the Sierra Leone and Kenya study has a significant/major impact on banks' financial performance. The study, therefore, exhibited a significant correlation between liquidity risk management and commercial bank financial return. If the liquidity issue is not resolved, this might lead to an inability of banks to fulfill their financial commitments and the customers' demands, which might also significantly impact the general banking sector. An optimum value of liquidity must be retained to increase operating efficiency and performance.

In addition, the study concludes that holdings of more assets would minimize returns for the commercial banks in Sierra Leone and Kenya in comparisons with the LATA or LDR. Therefore, commercial banks need to ensure that excess liquidity is not preserved. Commercial banks should also be sufficiently liquid to satisfy consumer requirements but not to the point of lower return as liquid assets result.

According to the descriptive analysis, ROA values were low in terms of the time provided by the low standard deviation. The ROA had a long right tail or positive skewness and it is clearly leptokurtic looking at the kurtosis value $36.3 > 3$. The Jarque-Bera statistics is the respective probability values and we clearly reject the distribution of the null hypothesis of the normal distribution for ROA because the probability valve is highly statistically significant. This distribution is clearly not normal.

The mean, median, Maximum, and Minimum and S.D values of the liquid assets to total assets (LATA) indicates a low variability in value over time. The LATA has a long right tail indicating a positive skewness it has a kurtosis value of $3.6 > 3$ indicating that is leptokurtic. We clearly reject the distribution of the null hypothesis of the normal distribution for LATA and mainly because the probability value is highly statistically significant.

Moreover, the mean, median, Maximum and Minimum, and standard deviation values of the LDR is also an indicator of the low volatility of the loan-to-deposit value. This

variable LDR mirrors a negative skewness and it is also leptokurtic because of the kurtosis value is $3.2 > 3$. We explicitly reject the null hypothesis distribution of the normal distribution for LATA, primarily because the probability value is highly significant.

The liquidity risk management ratio (LRMR) mean, median, Maximum and Minimum and standard deviation values were lower time variability as revealed by the lower standard deviation. The LRMR mirrors a negative skewness or has left tail and lower value than the sample mean and it is clearly leptokurtic as the kurtosis value is greater than 3 ($6.97 > 3$). We specifically reject the distribution of the null distribution hypothesis for LRMR mainly due to the high significant probability value

Finally, the capital adequacy ratio (CAR) mirrors appositve skewness (implies that this distribution has a long right tail and higher than the simple mean). The kurtosis value leptokurtic with ($17.7 > 3$). We explicitly reject the distribution of the zero-distribution ratio (CAR) hypothesis mainly because of the high significant probability value

From the correlation analysis, we can conclude that LATA and the LRMR are negatively correlated with the dependent variable ROA, Moreover, there is a positive correlation between other independent variables such as; LDR and CAR.

The Hausman test reveals that the probability value is highly statistically significant i.e., it is less than 0.05. So, from this result, we are rejecting the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative (fixed effect).

According to the outcome of the fixed effect Model, close observation of the coefficient reveals that the Liquid Asset -to-Total Asse (LATA), Loan- To -Deposit Ratio (LDR), and Liquidity Risk Management Ratio (LRMR) are the only statistically significant coefficients when using the fixed effect.

Moreover, one thing about the effect model reveals that the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable is seen as the upper bound. And in the fixed-effect model, it is seen

as the lower bound. The interpretation of this effects is that the parameter of the coefficient is 0.074406 and this is indicating a lower bound fixed effect

The probability p-value of the Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) is 0.7557 which is greater than 0.05. so, the CAR is not a significant independent variable for the regression model, or the Capital adequacy ratio (CAR) doesn't determine the dependent variable Return on Asset (ROA) in a good way. The capital adequacy ratio implies the bank's ability to retain adequate capital and management resources of the bank to recognize, calculate, track and regulate the risks that occur or might influence the value of bank capital. A further aspect that might also occur would be that banks are investing more in financial assets but are less careful about directing real sector funds and less supervising stagnant finance to cover some of the bank's capital (CAR) in the actual risk.

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APENDICES

Appendix 1: List of Commercial Banks in Sierra Leone

1. Sierra Leone Commercial Bank
2. Rokel Commercial Bank (SL) Limited
3. United Bank for Africa (SL) Limited

Appendix 2: List of Commercial Banks in Kenya

1. Kenya Commercial Bank Ltd
2. Standard Chartered Bank Ltd Kenya
3. Barclays Bank of Kenya Ltd

4. Ecobank Ltd of Kenya Ltd
5. UBA Bank of Kenya Ltd
6. National Bank of Kenya Ltd
7. Guaranty Trust Bank of Kenya Ltd
8. Diamond Trust Bank Kenya Ltd
9. Bank of Africa Kenya Ltd
10. Co-operative Bank of Kenya Ltd
11. Ecobank (SL) Limited
12. I&M Bank of Kenya Ltd
13. Bank of Baroda Ltd Kenya
14. Equity Bank Ltd Kenya
15. CFC Stanbic Bank Ltd Kenya
16. Consolidated Bank of Kenya Ltd
17. African Banking Corporation Ltd Kenya
18. Family Bank Ltd Kenya
19. Trans - National Bank Ltd Kenya
20. Development Bank of Kenya Ltd
21. Paramount Universal Bank Ltd
22. NIC Bank Ltd Kenya